

Table 1 - Exercises

Productive and unproductive AI-Human collaboration exercises

Productive	Unproductive
<p>P#01 – “The Generation Effect Activator” (1) Reading a technical article and writing an initial 50–100-word summary without AI, (2) submitting the summary to an AI model with the prompt "Here's my summary [paste]. What key points did I miss or misunderstand?", (3) revising the summary based on AI feedback, then (4) after distraction tasks, applying concepts to five novel scenarios.</p> <p>This exercise applies the generation effect (Bertsch et al., 2007; Slamecka & Graf, 1978) and productive failure principles (Kapur, 2008; Kapur & Bielaczyc, 2012), also delaying AI use until after initial encoding, which may support memory formation (Kosmyrna et al., 2025).</p>	<p>U#01 – “The Problem Solution Bypass” (1) Receiving a computational thinking problem, (2) immediately requesting a complete solution from AI, (3) copying the solution, then (4) following distraction, attempting a similar transfer problem independently.</p> <p>This design removes the struggle necessary for learning (O'Hara & Payne, 1998), contradicting productive failure principles (Kapur, 2008), and encourages cognitive offloading (Grinschgl et al., 2021; Sparrow et al., 2011) by preventing active problem-solving.</p>
<p>P#02 – “The Socratic AI Challenger” 1) Writing three arguments supporting a position on a controversial statement, (2) engaging with an AI model using the prompt "Act as a Socratic tutor on [topic]. Challenge my arguments with questions only: [arguments]", (3) refining arguments based on the exchange, then (4) after distraction tasks, generating three counterarguments with defenses independently.</p> <p>This exercise uses AI as a Socratic tutor (Elder & Paul, 1998; Ho et al., 2023; Orynbassarova & De Lasala Porta, 2024).</p>	<p>U#02 – “The Passive Summary Trap” (1) Receiving a complex academic article, (2) requesting an AI-generated bullet-point summary, (3) reviewing the summary passively, then (4) following distraction, explaining core concepts in simplified terms appropriate for a non-expert audience.</p> <p>This design theoretically produces shallow encoding (Kosmyrna et al., 2025) and impairs semantic retention (Abbas et al., 2024), preventing development of transferable conceptual understanding.</p>

Table 2 - MAI-AI Questionnaire

Questionnaire answered by participants pre and post study, separated by constructs and showcasing differences between pre and post questions.

Construct	Question	Post-study questionnaire
Attitudes	Q1	The use of AI makes me feel: Pessimistic (1) / Optimistic (5) about my future career prospects. =
	Q2	I believe using AI for my studies is: Detrimental (1) / Beneficial (5) for my learning outcomes. =
AI Engagement	Q3	I use AI tools (e.g.: ChatGPT, Gemini, Claude, Copilot) for my academic work. N/A
	Q4	I use AI to help me understand concepts when studying. I intend to use AI to help me understand concepts when studying.
	Q5	I use AI to help with brainstorming or generating new ideas for a task. I intend to use AI to help with brainstorming or generating new ideas for a task.
	Q6	I use AI tools to find the information needed for my work. I intend to use AI tools to find the information needed for my work.
	Q7	I use AI tools to check or verify my work before submission. I intend to use AI tools to check or verify my work before submission.
	Q8	I intend to use AI tools in my academic work in the future. =
	Q9	I am selective about when to use AI tools based on my learning goals. I intend to be selective about when to use AI tools based on my learning goals.
	Q10	I want to learn more about how to effectively use AI for learning. =
AI Literacy	Q11	I understand the basic principles of how AI systems work. =
	Q12	I am confident in my ability to use AI tools effectively for my studies and/or work. =
	Q13	I am aware of the different types of AI tools available and their capabilities. =
	Q14	I am aware of the limitations and potential biases in AI systems. =
	Q15	I know how to evaluate the quality and reliability of AI-generated outputs. =
Metacognitive Awareness	Q17	I am aware of how AI usage affects my own thinking processes. =
	Q18	I am conscious of how AI usage affects my memory and retention of information. =
	Q19	I am aware of when I use AI to avoid challenging cognitive tasks. =

	Q20	I am aware of how much I rely on AI while working on academic tasks.	=
	Q26	I can recognize when AI usage enhances versus hinders my learning.	=
Metacognitive Regulation	Q16	I decide how to approach a problem on my own before I ask an AI for a solution.	=
	Q21	I focus on understanding the information an AI tool provides, not just on getting an answer.	=
	Q22	I verify the accuracy of AI outputs before using them.	=
	Q23	If an AI tool gives me incorrect or unclear information, I try to solve the task on my own.	=
	Q24	After completing a task with AI, I evaluate what I have learned versus what the AI did for me.	=
	Q25	After completing a task with AI, I ask myself If I could have accomplished the task more effectively without using an AI tool.	=
Autonomy & Control	Q27	I feel control of my learning process when I use AI.	=
	Q28	I feel ownership of my work when I use AI.	=
	Q29	I limit my AI usage when I want to develop my own skills.	=

The equal “=” symbol means the question was identical in both pre and post questionnaires. Since Q3 was not relevant in the post questionnaire, it was not asked (N/A). Q16 and Q26 are sorted to be inside their constructs, instead of their order of appearance.

References

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